

Urban Relief

Dundee Pilot Report

D4.5

Document Factsheet

Grant agreement	101086638
Call identifier	Horizon-CL6-2022-Governance-01-08
Project title	Urban ReLeaf: Citizen-powered data ecosystems for inclusive and green urban transitions
Project start date	01/01/2023
Duration	48 months
Instrument	Horizon Europe
Type of action	Innovation action
Deliverable number	D4.5
Deliverable name	Dundee Pilot Report
Work package	WP4: Mobilize participants and implement Urban ReLeaf city pilots
Task	T4.3: Dundee: Citizen engagement for resilient BGI transitions
Deliverable lead	DCC
Deliverable type	Report
Due date	31/12/2025
Review completed	22/12/2025
Submission date	27/12/2025
Document version	1.0

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Acknowledgement

**Funded by
the European Union**

**UK Research
and Innovation**

Reference

Please cite this work as:

Hartley-Zels, J. (2025). Dundee Pilot Report. D4.5 for the Horizon Europe and Innovate UK co-funded project Urban ReLeaf under grant agreement IDs: 101086638, 10061290, and 10041792. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18015512.

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Short description	The D4.5 Dundee Pilot Report provides a summary of the Dundee City Pilot progress and activities from January 2024 to September 2025. It outlines the achievements, the key activities carried out and the anticipated next steps for Dundee City.
Keywords	Citizen science, urban resilience, greenspace planning, environmental health

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
SEN	Sensitive - limited under the conditions of the GA	
EU-R	Classified information - Restricted under EC Decision 2005/444	
EU-C	Classified information - Confidential under EC Decision 2005/444	

History			
Version	Date	Released by	Comment
0.1	26.09.2025	Johanna Hartley-Zels (DCC)	Draft version 1
0.2	24.10.2025	Todd Harwell (IIASA)	Review and suggested edits
0.3	15.12.2025	Johanna Hartley-Zels, Viola Marx (DCC)	Updated draft
0.4	22.12.2025	Todd Harwell (IIASA)	Add Appendix A items, review, and formatting
1.0	27.12.2025	Todd Harwell (IIASA)	Final version for submission

Project Partners

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Acronyms

DCC	Dundee City Council
IIASA	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
LoRaWAN	Long Range Wide Area Network
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SIMD	Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
SUDS	Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems
TRH	Temperature and Relative Humidity
UKCEH	UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology
UNIVDUN	University of Dundee
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The Urban ReLeaf Dundee pilot is part of a wider Horizon Europe initiative to co-create citizen-powered data ecosystems that support inclusive, climate-resilient urban transitions.

The Dundee pilot primarily focused on the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign, followed by a smaller-scale Air Quality Campaign. Both campaigns were designed to engage citizens in shaping the future of their city through participatory science and data collection.

Greenspace Perceptions Campaign

Launched in July 2024, the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign invited residents to share their experiences of Dundee's parks, play areas, and Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS). Through the Urban ReLeaf Cities app, web-based surveys, and redesigned paper formats, the campaign gathered perceptual, spatial, and environmental data across 43 greenspaces in all eight city wards. The campaign prioritised inclusion, with a target of 30-40% participation from marginalised communities, and used creative, pop-up engagement to reach residents where they naturally gather.

The campaign's three thematic strands, Park, Play, and SUDS, enabled the collection of diverse, community-sourced insights into how different types of greenspaces are experienced and valued across the city. Insights are already informing local planning frameworks such as the Open Space Strategy, Local Development Plan and Biodiversity Action Plan. The campaign also supported community-led initiatives, such as greenspace upgrades and funding bids, and demonstrated the value of citizen science in shaping equitable urban environments.

Air Quality Campaign

The Air Quality Campaign, initiated in October 2025, complements Dundee's active travel and public health goals by addressing vehicle idling near schools. Two low-cost air quality sensors will be installed outside selected schools to monitor pollution levels and raise awareness of the health and climate impacts of car emissions. The campaign aims to engage students in real-world STEM learning and promote behaviour change through citizen science. It builds on partnerships with Dundee City Council's Active Transport team and aligns with broader efforts to reduce emissions and improve air quality in vulnerable communities.

While still in early stages, the Air Quality Campaign is expected to generate valuable environmental data and foster intergenerational engagement around clean air and sustainable mobility.

Background on the Urban ReLeaf Project and City Pilots

Urban ReLeaf promotes collaboration between local communities and public authorities to address urgent climate issues and support innovations that enable more just and green urban transitions. The project addresses the challenges of increasing environmental stresses in urban areas, accentuated inequalities in access to high-quality greenspace, lack of suitable data for planning and decision making as well as inclusion in public participation in science and research.

The main objectives of Urban ReLeaf are to:

- Understand current data ecosystem and urban greening and participation policies in six pilot cities and co-develop opportunities for citizen science and citizen participation to complement existing practices.
- Mobilise and empower local communities in issues of public interest surrounding urban green infrastructure and environmental stewardship.
- Support the long-term inclusion of active and passive data from citizens within official data streams for urban monitoring, planning and innovation in public policy.
- Encourage knowledge exchange and training across relevant actors beyond the six pilot cities by establishing a community of practice and an accelerator programme.
- Offer flexible and innovative ways of governance that can underpin inclusive green urban planning in support of the European Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In pursuit of urban climate resilience, six Urban ReLeaf pilot cities co-create participatory, and data-driven innovations to democratise urban greenspace monitoring and the wider policy making process.

In Dundee, the project responds to urgent local challenges including climate vulnerability, unequal access to quality greenspaces, and gaps in data for inclusive planning. The initiative builds on Dundee's commitment to sustainability, health equity, and community wealth building, aligning with strategic frameworks such as the Open Space Strategy, Local Development Plan, and Net-Zero Transition Plan.

The Dundee pilot primarily focuses on greenspace perceptions, inviting residents to share their experiences of parks, play areas, and Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS). Through a combination of digital tools, paper surveys, and in-person engagement, Urban ReLeaf Dundee gathers spatial, perceptual, and environmental data to inform policy and planning. The campaign prioritises underrepresented communities, with a target of 30% of responses from areas of high deprivation, as classified by the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation, and works closely with local organisations such as Douglas Community Spaces Group, ScrapAntics, Maxwell Centre, Transform Community Development and community gardens to ensure inclusive participation. The Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) is a detailed analysis of deprived areas based on many key measures of deprivation including health, employment, income, housing, education, crime and access to basic services. Visualisation of the SMID can be found at [SIMD \(Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation\)](#).

In addition to the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign, Urban ReLeaf Dundee will install two low-cost air quality sensors outside selected schools identified as having issues with vehicle idling near school gates. This initiative complements the work of Dundee City Council's Active Transport team by reinforcing messaging around active travel to school and raising awareness of the health and climate impacts of air pollution from cars. By involving schools directly, the campaign not only supports public health and wellbeing goals but also provides students with real-world STEM learning opportunities through environmental monitoring and citizen science.

Urban ReLeaf Dundee also serves as a testbed for data innovation, integrating citizen-generated insights into council systems via GIS mapping and supporting cross-departmental collaboration. The pilot contributes to broader goals of climate resilience, biodiversity, and social justice, while laying the groundwork for future citizen science initiatives in the city.

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1 Greenspace Perceptions Campaign

The Greenspace Perceptions Campaign is a core component of Dundee's Urban ReLeaf initiative, a city-wide citizen science project aimed at enhancing the quality, accessibility, and inclusivity of urban greenspaces. Launched in July 2024, the campaign invites residents to share their experiences and perceptions of local parks and green areas through the Urban ReLeaf Cities app, web-based surveys, and paper formats. This 15 month-long data collection effort was designed to build a robust, community-generated evidence base that will inform future greenspace planning and policy decisions. The campaign focuses on three key themes, Park, Play, and SUDS, each exploring different aspects of greenspace use and value, from recreational play areas to climate-adaptive infrastructure.

The project started with interviews with key stakeholders within Dundee City Council followed by design of the Urban ReLeaf Cities App alongside IIASA. The app then went through a round of testing with local community groups to test useability and design before being launched to the public in July 2024. The app underwent changes in response to public and internal feedback, including the addition of a "like" and "dislike" button feature that allows individuals to quickly share a perception along with a photograph. This feature proved popular with the public and became the most used way participants shared feedback through the app.

The campaign officially began with a public launch event at Baxter Park Pavilion on 17 July 2024 (Figure 1), attended by local stakeholders including Dundee City Council, the University of Dundee, and community organisations. Since then, Urban ReLeaf has engaged residents across the city through pop-up events, volunteer-led outreach, and a photo competition celebrating Dundee's unique green environments. The first phase of the campaign ran until the end of summer 2025, with data being continuously gathered and analysed to support city-level strategies on health, biodiversity, and climate resilience.

Figure 1. Public launch of Dundee's Greenspace Perceptions Campaign at Baxter Park Pavilion

1.1 Context and Objectives

The Greenspace Perceptions Campaign was developed in response to a pressing local challenge: ensuring equitable access to high-quality urban greenspaces across Dundee. Despite the well-documented benefits of greenspace-including improved physical and mental health, enhanced child development, and stronger community cohesion-access remains uneven, particularly in areas of high deprivation.

This disparity is compounded by climate-related pressures such as increased flooding, heat stress, and biodiversity loss, which disproportionately affect vulnerable communities and urban environments.

The campaign aligns with multiple strategic priorities at local, national, and European levels. Locally, it supports Dundee's Open Space Strategy and the Local Development Plan, both of which aim to create inclusive, resilient, and biodiverse urban environments. Regionally and nationally, the campaign contributes to Scotland's ambitions for climate adaptation and community wellbeing, as outlined in the National Planning Framework 4 and the Climate Change Plan. At the EU level, Urban ReLeaf is part of a Horizon Europe-funded initiative involving six cities across Europe, including Dundee, to co-create citizen-powered data ecosystems that inform nature-based solutions for urban sustainability.

The overarching objectives of the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign are threefold:

1. To gather inclusive, location-specific data on how residents perceive and use greenspaces, with a target of 30% of responses coming from areas of high deprivation.
2. To empower citizens through participatory tools such as the Urban ReLeaf Cities app, paper surveys, and public events, enabling them to shape the future design and management of greenspaces.
3. To inform policy and planning by integrating citizen-generated insights into strategic frameworks that address climate resilience, health equity, and urban biodiversity.

By centring community voices and lived experiences, the campaign seeks to ensure that greenspace development in Dundee is not only environmentally sustainable but also socially just. The data will inform Dundee City Council's policies and strategies, ensuring that urban greenspaces are developed in ways that are inclusive, sustainable, and responsive to community needs. By involving the community in data collection and encouraging collaboration, we aim to improve the city's greenspaces, promote environmental sustainability, and ensure that the voices of underrepresented groups are heard.

Data includes:

- Methods used to access greenspaces and ease of doing so
- Perceptions of safety
- Time spent in greenspaces
- Wildlife observations
- Qualitative data on what people want from greenspaces, play areas, and SUDS
- Perceptions of litter/maintenance/quality
- Large volume of photos shared across surveys including love/dislike/flood/drought
- Demographic data for respondents

In addition, the following metadata is collected:

- Latitude and longitude of survey response
- Date of response

By combining citizen science with spatial and qualitative data, the campaign offers an innovative model for participatory urban planning. Its methodology and findings have the potential to inform similar initiatives across the Urban ReLeaf network and other European cities.

1.2 Design and Implementation

The first phase of designing the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign involved a series of interviews with colleagues in other Dundee City Council departments including Greenspace and Biodiversity, Environmental Health, Community Planning, Community Wealth Building and Urban Planning. Colleagues in these departments have also had the opportunity for regular updates on the project and to provide feedback to ensure the findings are relevant to current council priorities and workstreams.

From these interviews, the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign was designed to gather inclusive, location-specific data on how Dundee residents and visitors perceive and interact with urban greenspaces across the city. By aligning the survey with the [Place Standard Tool](#) used by council planning departments findings align with existing council work and policies, encapsulating all important aspects of how people use a space. The campaign explores how individuals and communities experience and value their local greenspaces, with a particular focus on inclusivity, accessibility, and climate resilience.

In the second phase once the survey and Urban ReLeaf Cities App was built, a round of testing took place with communities to look at useability. Some changes were made to improve the user experience of the app. When the app was first launched, park surveys were split into “Movement”, “Safety”, and “Space”. Feedback was that this created a cluttered map and some surveys were not being filled in as a result. These surveys were then put together to form one “Park” survey per greenspace and the distance to the survey point on the map was increased so that individuals did not need to be as close to the geographical point for the survey. Feedback was that the initial parameters were too tight and people preferred not to complete the survey if it was not on their planned route through the park. This was particularly challenging in larger parks where the survey point could be a long walk from where the participant entered the park or planned to spend their time.

Feedback from community events, when asked about whether individuals and groups were using the app, was that for some groups, for example community gardeners, older demographics and youth groups, particularly those under 18, using a phone app was challenging. A paper version of the survey was therefore made available and later revised to re-design the survey to make it attractive to disseminate at events and through ballot boxes placed at a range of spaces across the city, including libraries, community centres and Universities.

The campaign was structured around three thematic strands Park, Play, and SUDS, each representing a distinct aspect of urban greenspace. The Park survey asked questions about general park use with results feeding into the Open Space Strategy. The Play survey relates to children’s play areas with results used by planning officers for the Play Sufficiency Assessment and Local Development Plans. The SUDS survey helps monitor ongoing flood and water management work carried out by city engineers. These themes were selected to reflect both everyday lived experiences and strategic planning priorities. The campaign’s core message, “*Share your perceptions, shape your city*”, highlighted the power of community voices in influencing urban design and policy. Complementing this was the campaign’s slogan, “*Discover, Connect, Thrive,*” which invited participants to explore their local greenspaces, build connections with nature and community, and contribute to a healthier, more resilient urban environment.

Key Partners and Stakeholders

Key partners included Dundee City Council, the University of Dundee, and a wide range of community organisations such as the Maxwell Centre, Douglas Community Spaces Group, Campy Growers, ScrapAntics, RSPB Scotland, and Scottish Water.

- **The University of Dundee**
- **Dundee City Council** led research design, coordinated community engagement and integrated findings into local planning frameworks.
- **Community partners** played a vital role in outreach, particularly in engaging vulnerable groups.
- A growing network of **Urban ReLeaf volunteers**, including students, retirees, and local residents (Figure 2), acted as campaign ambassadors, facilitating survey participation and building trust within communities.

Figure 2. Urban ReLeaf Volunteers and DCC Research Officer, Jennifer Dunn, with pop-up banner.

Communication and Outreach

A multi-channel communication strategy was employed, combining digital tools with face-to-face engagement. Participants could contribute via the Urban ReLeaf Cities app, web-based surveys, or paper surveys--the latter introduced in 2025 to improve accessibility and reach digitally excluded groups. The paper survey was redesigned in August 2025 by Lauren Bloor, University of Dundee, to enable those who are more digitally excluded to participate more easily in participating (see Appendix A). Additionally, this allowed for the surveys to be placed throughout the city at various venues including community centres, libraries and community groups. Outreach activities included pop-up events in parks, universities, cultural organisations and community centres, as well as collaborations with festivals, community events and school programmes (Figure 3). The campaign also featured creative engagement

formats such as art activities, guided walks, a photo competition and the “Nature Detectives” citizen science event.

Special attention was given to engaging vulnerable and hard-to-reach groups, including residents in areas of high deprivation, older adults, children and New Scots communities. The New Scots programme is a collaborative initiative aimed at integrating refugees and asylum seekers into Scottish communities. These audiences were prioritised due to their heightened vulnerability to environmental and health inequalities. Engagement was facilitated through trusted intermediaries, repeat visits, and accessible formats. For example, Urban ReLeaf partnered with ScrapAntics to deliver activities for refugees and collaborated with schools and universities to involve students in field-based data collection. Transform Community Development, a Dundee-based organisation that works with vulnerable individuals within the city to provide accommodation, support, advice and opportunities, involved groups they work with by organising visits to the local parks and filling out surveys.

Figure 3. Urban ReLeaf Volunteers and DCC Research Officer, Johanna Hartley-Zels, at Lochee Easter Fun Day.

Campaign Evolution and Adaptation

The campaign evolved significantly across 2024 and 2025 in response to community feedback and operational learning. Key adaptations included:

- Expansion of paper survey distribution via ballot boxes in libraries and community centres (Figure 4).
- Integration of Urban ReLeaf into school programmes such as Climate Ready Classrooms.

- Discussions with DCC Greenspace, Open Space and Planning teams to identify data gaps and target underrepresented council wards.
- Provision of evidence-based insights to support community-led funding applications, such as greenspace upgrades at Keswick Terrace Park.
- Support for Dundee City Council's bid to the Nature Towns and Cities programme. Although the proposal, "Dundee: A Nature Literate City", was not successful, the campaign demonstrated the value of citizen-generated data in shaping strategic proposals and advocating for investment in urban nature.

These adaptations ensured the campaign remained responsive, equitable, and representative of Dundee's diverse population, while building a robust evidence base to inform future greenspace planning and policy.

Figure 4. Re-designed Dundee Greenspace Perceptions survey and ballot box at Blend, Baxter Park.

Communication with the Public

To raise awareness and encourage participation in the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign, a variety of public-facing communication tools were deployed across Dundee's greenspaces, community venues, and events.

32 "Wild Grass" and "Bee-Friendly" signs were installed in parks and greenspaces across the city (Figure 5). These signs served as both educational prompts and visual markers of the campaign's presence, encouraging passers-by to reflect on biodiversity and engage with Urban ReLeaf. Their installation was coordinated with Dundee City Council's greenspace maintenance teams and timed to align with seasonal planting and mowing schedules to ensure visibility and relevance.

Figure 5. Urban ReLeaf Wild Grass sign "Shape Your City" at South Road Park.

Posters featuring a QR code were displayed at events and in public venues (Figure 6). The QR code linked to a dedicated Linktree page hosted on the Sustainable Dundee website, where participants could:

- Download the Urban ReLeaf Cities app
- Complete the web-based greenspace perception survey
- Learn more about the campaign
- Sign up for the Urban ReLeaf newsletter
- Register interest in volunteering
- Access a live map showing locations where newly designed paper surveys could be picked up and deposited (since September 2025)

These posters were also placed in Dundee City Council office kitchens, community centres, and other high-footfall locations to reach a broad audience, including council staff and local residents.

A7 Postcards featuring the same QR code were distributed at events and through partner organisations (Figure 7). These compact, eye-catching materials were designed for easy sharing and takeaway, helping to extend the campaign's reach beyond formal engagement settings.

Together, these communication tools supported a layered outreach strategy that combined visibility in public spaces with digital accessibility, ensuring that residents could engage with Urban ReLeaf in ways that suited their preferences and circumstances.

Figure 6. Urban ReLeaf "Shape Your City" poster Graphic.

Figure 7. Urban ReLeaf promotional A7 postcards.

1.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used

The Greenspace Perceptions Campaign was implemented across a wide range of neighbourhoods and greenspaces throughout Dundee, with 43 greenspaces and parks surveys spread across all 8 wards of the city.

Priority was given to the wards and greenspaces with the largest data gaps (Lochee, Colleside and North East Wards), as well as taking advantage of events and activities taking place in the parks that helped us reach a wide range of individuals including vulnerable audiences that may be interested in engaging in citizen science activities.

A suite of technologies supported the campaign's citizen science activities and enabled inclusive, multi-format data collection:

- **Urban ReLeaf Cities App:** A mobile application allowing residents to record and share their perceptions of greenspaces in real time (Figure 8). The app offers an interactive and accessible way to contribute geolocated data and photographs.

Figure 8. Map of greenspace survey sites in the app.

- **Web-Based Surveys (Partimap):** Accessible via browser, these surveys allowed users to provide feedback on the three thematic areas, **Park**, **Play**, and **SUDS**, without needing to download an app. This format was particularly useful for engaging participants that do not want to download an app.
- **Paper Surveys:** Introduced more broadly to the campaign in 2025 to improve accessibility for digitally excluded groups. 5,000 redesigned copies of the paper survey as shown in Figure 9 (full survey in Appendix A) were distributed via libraries, community centres, and ballot boxes placed in venues near greenspaces. From September 2025, a live map was made available via the Sustainable Dundee website, showing where paper surveys could be picked up and returned.
- **GIS Mapping Tools:** Used internally to visualise data gaps, monitor engagement, and support strategic planning. These tools helped identify underrepresented Council wards and informed targeted outreach efforts.

Figure 9. Paper copies of Dundee's Greenspace Perception Surveys.

Accessibility and usability adaptations were central to the campaign's design. These included:

- **On-site demonstrations** and **volunteer-led support** at events
- **Attractively designed survey formats** to encourage participation
- **Multimedia content** (videos and photos) shared via social media
- **QR-coded posters and A7 postcards** linking to a central Linktree page hosted on the Sustainable Dundee website, where participants could:
 - Download the app
 - Complete the web survey
 - Learn more about the campaign
 - Sign up for the newsletter
 - Register interest in volunteering
 - Access the paper survey map (since September 2025)

These tools and adaptations ensured that the campaign was not only technologically robust but also inclusive and responsive to the needs of diverse communities. Vulnerable groups,

including older adults, New Scots, and residents in deprived areas, were engaged through trusted intermediaries, repeat visits, and tailored activities, ensuring broad participation in shaping Dundee's greenspace future. These efforts ensured that the technologies used were not only functional but also inclusive, enabling broad participation in shaping Dundee's greenspace future.

Urban ReLeaf's data and insights will contribute to several key Dundee City Council policies and initiatives, including:

- **Local Development Plan** - Sets out the city's long-term vision for land use and development. It provides a framework for decision-making on planning applications and guides the sustainable growth of Dundee, shaping policies on housing, infrastructure, economic development, greenspaces, and environmental sustainability.
- **Climate Action Plan** - Supporting Dundee's efforts to reduce carbon emissions and adapt to climate change.
- **Sustainable Transport Strategy** - Enhancing green corridors and active travel routes.
- **Biodiversity Action Plan** - Ensuring urban greening efforts contribute to biodiversity conservation.
- **Open Space Strategy** - Aims to enhance the management and quality of public greenspaces

1.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection

Citizen participation was central to the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign, with residents contributing perceptual, spatial, and environmental data to inform the future of Dundee's urban greenspaces. Participants shared their experiences and preferences through three main thematic lenses, Park, Play, and SUDS, capturing how different types of greenspaces are used, valued, and perceived across the city. Participants contributed perceptual data including personal experiences, preferences and feedback on greenspace quality, accessibility, and use. Spatial data included geolocated submissions via mobile app and description of location via Partimap surveys submitted via paper survey or web survey.

Data collection was facilitated through a combination of tools:

- **The Urban ReLeaf Cities app** enabled real-time geolocated submissions, allowing users to record their perceptions directly within greenspaces.
- **Web-based surveys** hosted on the Partimap platform provided an accessible alternative for desktop users.
- **Paper surveys**, redesigned and widely distributed in 2025, were introduced to improve accessibility for digitally excluded groups and those that prefer not to use technology when providing feedback. These were collected via ballot boxes placed in libraries, community centres, and venues near parks as well as used during engagement events and pop-ups.

The greenspace perceptions survey asks questions at 43 greenspace locations with one survey asking questions on the themes of "space", "movement", and "safety". There are 26 play survey locations, and 16 SUDS survey locations. See Appendix B – List of Dundee Parks and Greenspaces Surveyed for a list of Parks and Greenspaces surveyed through the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign.

Love/dislike/flood/drought responses can be submitted across the whole city in both the app and web-based survey. This allows participants to drop a pin on the map and tell us more in their own words. Responses for the like and dislike span a range of topics and preliminary

findings, which were reported back to stakeholders in an update meeting in March 2020, show the following:

What encourages park use:

- Routes/Accessibility - clear paths, quiet roads with interest
- Nice views, things to look at, art
- Safety - Lighting and "eyes on the street"

What discourages park use:

- Routes/Accessibility - heavy traffic
- Litter, dog dirt, vandalism
- No sign of progress/ complaints not addressed

Urban ReLeaf Dundee: Community Engagement Approach

Dundee City Council aims, through the Urban ReLeaf Greenspace Perceptions campaign, to bridge data gaps in park usage and environmental insights, with a focus on underrepresented wards and communities. This strategy outlined how we collected meaningful, inclusive data by leveraging existing networks, community groups, and events while promoting citizen science and accessibility. The key priorities identified were:

- **Targeting Data Gaps:** We focused on areas with limited existing data, particularly in wards experiencing high deprivation. These were identified by the Dundee City Council Greenspace, Open Space and Planning Teams as Lochee, Coldside, Northeast and Strathmartine wards. However, it was agreed that all Wards would benefit from the data gathered in the campaign.
- **Inclusive Participation:** We aimed for at least 30% of responses to come from vulnerable communities through targeted outreach and collaboration with trusted facilitators.
- **Community-led Approach:** We partnered with local groups and events to maximise engagement and relevance.
- **Multi-channel Communication:** We used digital tools, paper surveys, and ambassador support to overcome accessibility barriers.

Engagement was ongoing, with seasonal peaks aligned to public events, school programmes, and community activities held in the parks. A pop-up model was used to meet people where they already gather-parks, libraries, community centres, and cultural venues.

Inclusive Community Involvement

Dundee City Council recognised the importance of diverse voices in shaping the future of Dundee's greenspaces. The engagement approach was designed to ensure broad participation, especially from underserved communities.

The campaign placed a strong emphasis on reaching vulnerable and hard-to-reach groups, particularly in areas of high deprivation. Urban ReLeaf Dundee partnered with trusted community organisations to support inclusive engagement efforts. Collaborations with groups such as Hot Chocolate Trust, Dundee Youth Council, and ScrapAntics enabled meaningful participation from youth, older adults, disabled individuals, and New Scots. ScrapAntics Family Club played a particularly important role in engaging families from diverse backgrounds. To extend outreach further, Urban ReLeaf Dundee worked closely with community centres, schools, and local organisations to connect with residents who might otherwise be excluded from such initiatives. These efforts were supported by Dundee City Council Communities Officers, who provided local knowledge and facilitation in various events and activities (Figure 10). In addition, the project team participated in university-led field trips to local parks and SUDS sites, integrating data collection with environmental education for students.

Figure 10. Engaging the community at Keswick Park during a public consultation, with Dundee City Council teams and ScrapAntics.

Engaging with Local Networks & Events

Urban ReLeaf Dundee adopted a pop-up engagement model that integrated with existing community activities and events held in parks and neighbourhoods, an example of which is shown in Figure 11. This approach enabled the project team to meet residents where they naturally gathered, making participation more accessible while optimising time and resources. In addition to embedding engagement within established events, targeted activities were organised in underutilised greenspaces and communities that are typically underrepresented in environmental initiatives. Regular stakeholder update meetings were held to keep the wider community and key partners informed of project developments. To support deeper dialogue and collaboration, focus groups were convened with individuals and organisations sharing common interests, such as “Friends of Parks” groups that actively support local parks. Urban ReLeaf Dundee also delivered its own activities, including the *Nature Detectives* programme in Douglas Park (Figure 12), and developed a volunteer programme to support citizen science. Through this initiative, citizen science ambassadors were trained to assist others in using the Urban ReLeaf app and contributing data. The project team also engaged with local networks such as the Sustainable Dundee Network and worked closely with departments across Dundee City Council, including the Sustainability and Climate Change Team, Greenspace Team, Urban Planning, and Active Transport, to align efforts with strategic frameworks such as the Open Space Strategy, Biodiversity Action Plan, Local Development Plan, and Net-Zero Transition Plan.

Figure 11. Urban ReLeaf table at the Maxwell Centre Wildlife Fair, engaging young citizen scientists in gardening for nature.

Figure 12. Young participant engaging with nature at Douglas Wee Forest during Nature Detectives, collecting data for Urban ReLeaf and the City Nature Challenge.

Demographic and Inclusion Monitoring

While personal data collection was minimised in line with GDPR, demographic indicators such as postcode, age group, and community affiliation were used to monitor inclusion and diversity. This supported Urban ReLeaf's KPI targets of 30-40% participation from marginalised groups and 50% female participation, as outlined in the original proposal.

In line with Urban ReLeaf project guidelines, vulnerable groups are defined as those who may experience barriers to participation in urban decision-making and environmental initiatives.

Pop-Up Community Lab

We further engaged citizens through the Pop-Up Community Lab activities. This involved commissioning an artist to deliver a series of lantern making workshops leading up to the Dundee Hooley. Urban ReLeaf, in partnership with Dundee City Council Events Team, invited proposals from artists to design and deliver a series of lantern-making workshops inspired by Dundee's greenspaces and water-themed data, engaging participants in creative expression while fostering dialogue around urban nature, sustainability, and community identity.

The workshops were designed to highlight Urban ReLeaf to participants and encourage them to creatively express their own connection to water in greenspaces in Dundee. The lanterns served as a catalyst for those communities to share their perceptions, have a creative outlet and create community cohesion.

These workshops culminated in a lantern parade as part of the Dundee Hooley on Sunday 30 November, celebrating St Andrew's Day. The Dundee Hooley is an annual celebration of St Andrew and his values of kindness and welcome. This year the parade will focus on St Andrew, the fisherman, and will have a water theme. Following the parade, participants were allowed to keep the lanterns, where they will act as a project reminder and also a talking point for participants to share their experience with their networks, further increasing project impact reach.

1.5 Findings and Reflections

The Greenspace Perceptions Campaign successfully engaged a wide cross-section of Dundee's population, with a strong emphasis on inclusivity, creativity, and community-led data collection. Over 15 months, the campaign gathered perceptual, spatial, and environmental data from 43 greenspaces across all eight city wards, with a particular focus on underrepresented areas such as Lochee, Coldside, and North East (Table 1). Preliminary analysis by VUB done in March 20205 suggests the campaign is likely to meet its KPI of 30-40% participation from marginalised groups, supported by a multi-format approach (app, web, and paper surveys) and targeted outreach through trusted intermediaries.

Table 1: Overview of submissions for the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign

Type	# of submissions
Digital Surveys (Web)	135
Digital Surveys (App)	322
Paper Surveys*	113
Love/dislike/flood/drought observations	901
Photographs	1362

*Final count is still pending collection from ballot boxes in libraries and community centres.

A key success factor was the pop-up engagement model, which allowed the team to meet residents where they already gathered including at community events, parks, and cultural venues. This approach proved more effective in driving participation than general awareness or share-back events. For example, app usage and survey completion rates were higher at large-scale events such as the Lochee Easter Fun Day and Douglas Park's *Nature Detectives* than at standalone information sessions. Reaching a critical mass of participants often required being present in parks during peak times or working directly with community groups.

Arts-based engagement, such as inviting people of all ages to add to a collage, draw or write what they would like to see in their ideal park while engaging with individuals at events, the Urban ReLeaf Dundee photo competition and the upcoming lantern-making workshops, proved effective in sparking curiosity and dialogue, particularly among families and young people who may not typically engage in formal consultation processes or who may not be familiar with citizen science.

Data Analysis Approach: Turning Citizen Insights into Actionable Evidence

To ensure that the rich dataset collected through the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign informs policy and planning meaningfully, a comprehensive analysis plan was developed by the University of Dundee in collaboration with Dundee City Council. The analysis aims to translate citizen-generated data into actionable insights for strategic frameworks such as the Open Space Strategy, Local Development Plan, and Biodiversity Action Plan. Urban ReLeaf aims to share insights from data analysis from the Greenspace Perceptions Campaign with relevant council departments, such as Planning, the first quarter of 2026.

The dataset includes spatial, quantitative, and qualitative data collected via the Urban ReLeaf Cities app, web-based Partimap surveys, and paper surveys. These were cleaned, merged, and prepared for analysis, with spatial data clipped to the Dundee City Council boundary and demographic data used to monitor inclusion.

Key analytical methods include:

- **Descriptive statistics** to summarise trends across closed-ended questions, visualised through bar charts, box plots, and Sankey diagrams.
- **Sociodemographic analysis** (led by VUB) to assess inclusivity and representation, including gender, age, and education level comparisons with census data.
- **Spatial analysis** using ArcGIS tools such as Kernel Density and Hotspot Analysis to identify clusters of activity and statistically significant patterns in how residents perceive and use greenspaces.
- **Distance analysis** to estimate how far participants travel to access greenspaces, based on postcode data.
- **Overlay analysis** to explore the types of land cover associated with places people love or dislike, using UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology (UKCEH) and OS Open Greenspace datasets.
- **Qualitative analysis** of open-ended responses and uploaded images using thematic content analysis and coding in NVivo, to uncover deeper insights into public perceptions and values.

The analysis will be conducted on data collected up to the end of December 2025, with results expected in early 2026. These findings will be shared through community events and used to support scenario planning and future greenspace interventions.

Volunteer Quotes

"A few weeks ago, I had the opportunity to volunteer at the Keswick Park public consultation with Urban ReLeaf, marking my first ever hands-on experience in community engagement. We connected with local families, handed out surveys, and most importantly, heard directly

from the park's youngest users. From nature hunts to creative idea-sharing activities, the children's energy and imagination made the day vibrant and inspiring. This experience reminded me that good planning begins with listening to stories, aspirations, and the everyday needs of the people we design for. I truly enjoyed spending time with the community and learning what matters most in their shared spaces." (KJ - Urban ReLeaf Volunteer)

"I had the pleasure of volunteering at the Easter Family Fun Day at Lochee Park as part of the Urban ReLeaf initiative. It was such a rewarding experience engaging with children through creative colouring activities and speaking with parents about the importance of community-led environmental monitoring. We encouraged visitors to try the Urban ReLeaf app and fill in the questionnaire to support the research around greener urban spaces. The day was full of positive energy, great conversations, and place-based learning. I had the chance to meet and work alongside inspiring people" (MS - Urban ReLeaf Volunteer)

1.6 Recommendations and Future Steps

The Greenspace Perceptions Campaign will continue to inform Dundee's strategic planning and community engagement efforts beyond summer 2025. Data collected through the campaign is already being used to support:

- Greenspace upgrades (e.g. Keswick Terrace Park, Strathmartine Connections, Douglas Connections and the Dighty Burn Restoration Project).
- Planning frameworks such as the Local Development Plan and Biodiversity Action Plan.
- Community-led proposals and funding applications.
- Cross-departmental collaboration within Dundee City Council, including Planning, Environment, and Climate Change teams.

In early 2026, Urban ReLeaf intends to host share-back events to present findings to communities and stakeholders. This may involve discussions around how the community can use the data gathered to make improvements in their own communities and advocate for their community greenspaces.

The campaign's success in Dundee offers a replicable model for other cities seeking to embed citizen science into urban planning. Key strategies include:

- Multi-format data collection (app, web, paper) to ensure digital inclusion.
- Pop-up engagement at existing community events to reduce barriers to participation and gather a larger number of citizens at one time.
- Partnerships with trusted intermediaries to reach vulnerable groups.
- Use of GIS mapping to identify data gaps and guide outreach.
- Integration with school and university programmes to build long-term engagement.

For future iterations, cities could consider developing toolkits for community groups and potentially offering micro-grants for local engagement. While the air quality sensor campaign is designed as a short-term initiative, Urban ReLeaf recognises the importance of fostering sustained relationships that extend beyond individual projects. Long-term engagement involves building ongoing connections between Dundee City Council's Sustainability and Climate Change Team and local schools. This is achieved by providing hands-on activities, co-created learning resources, and opportunities for students to explore environmental data in meaningful ways. By embedding these practices into school programmes, the aim is to support climate literacy, encourage stewardship, and create lasting pathways for collaboration between educators, young people, and city teams.

2 Air Quality Campaign

The Air Quality Monitoring Campaign marks the second phase of the Urban ReLeaf Dundee project, launched in 2025. Building on the community engagement and greenspace insights developed during the first phase, this new chapter shifts focus to the quality of the air we breathe--particularly around schools where children are most vulnerable to pollution.

Many parents drop their children off at the school gates leading to elevated emissions where children enter school. One of the aims of the air quality campaign is to support messaging from colleagues in active transport by monitoring the emissions in real-time and showing the difference between when cars are idling in front of the school compared to times when cars are not dropping off or picking up. The hope is this will encourage parents to consider using alternative modes of transport, or at the very least, turning their engines off while they wait.

The campaign also introduces citizen science to school pupils in Dundee, giving them the opportunity to engage directly with environmental data, explore real-world science, and contribute to local action on air quality. By combining education, behaviour change, and real-time monitoring, the campaign empowers young people and their communities to better understand and respond to the impacts of traffic-related emissions.

This phase is being piloted at two schools, Glebelands Primary and North East Campus, and is designed to support both learning and local policy goals. Key milestones include:

- **Early 2025:** Campaign planning and stakeholder engagement, selection of suitable schools.
- **Spring 2025:** Strategic pivot from vegetation impact monitoring to behaviour-focused school zone monitoring.
- **Summer 2025:** Development of off-grid sensor systems using mobile routers and battery packs.
- **Autumn 2025:** testing of off-grid sensor systems and checking viability of the project. School outreach and site preparation for sensor installation.

2.1 Context and Objectives

Local Challenges and Urgency

Air pollution, particularly from road traffic, is a growing concern in Dundee, with measurable impacts on public health, especially for children. Schools located near busy roads often experience elevated levels of nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), which are linked to asthma, reduced lung development, and other long-term health risks. Idling vehicles during school drop-off and pick-up times exacerbate these issues, creating pollution hotspots at the school gate.

This challenge is considered urgent due to its disproportionate impact on children, who are more vulnerable to air pollution due to their developing respiratory systems and higher breathing rates. Addressing this issue is critical not only for immediate health outcomes but also for fostering long-term behavioural change around sustainable travel and environmental responsibility. This campaign supports efforts made by colleagues in active travel to raise awareness of the health and climate implications of idling by showing data on the air pollution. Our ambition is that this campaign helps to reduce idling at the school gates and encourages families to switch to active travel, such as walking or cycling, to school

Policy Context

The campaign aligns with several local, national, and European policy priorities:

- **Local:** Dundee's Climate Action Plan and Active Travel Strategy both emphasise reducing transport emissions and promoting healthier, low-carbon lifestyles.
- **National:** The Scottish Government's Cleaner Air for Scotland 2 (CAFS2) strategy sets out a vision for achieving the best air quality in Europe, with a strong focus on protecting children and schools.

By embedding air quality monitoring in schools, the campaign contributes to these frameworks while fostering local ownership and awareness.

Campaign Objectives

The overarching objectives of the Air Quality Monitoring Campaign are to:

- **Generate hyperlocal air quality data** in school zones to inform behaviour change and policy.
- **Raise awareness** among pupils, parents, and staff about the health impacts of traffic pollution.
- **Support curriculum-linked learning** by providing real-time data for use in science, geography, and maths education.
- **Encourage sustainable travel behaviours** such as walking, cycling, and reduced idling.
- **Build capacity for citizen science** and environmental stewardship within school communities.

2.2 Design and Implementation

The design of the Air Quality Monitoring Campaign evolved significantly over the course of 2025, reflecting both technical learning and strategic realignment.

Firstly, Dundee City Council had planned to adopt 60 temperature and relative humidity (TRH) sensors and implement a heat stress campaign using volunteers. Dundee City Council were initially provided with two TRH sensors, however, after in house testing, there were a number of issues flagged, most notably with data capture and connectivity issues as Dundee is not connected to the long-range wide area network (LoRaWAN) or Helium networks. For example, if a person was stationary for too long, the sensor would stop collecting data. We also found that when the weather was cold, the sensor was not accurate as it was measuring considerable higher temperatures than outdoors as body heat affected the results. The campaign was therefore deemed unfeasible to implement by the council who chose to focus on the Greenspace and Air Quality Campaigns. The University of Dundee was keen to use the TRH sensors and develop a campaign, therefore the sensors were passed to the University of Dundee.

Initially, the Air Quality Campaign was conceived as a small-scale pilot using two sensors to explore the role of vegetation in mitigating air pollution, the campaign has since pivoted toward a more behaviour-focused approach centred on school zones and vehicle idling.

Initial Concept and Design

The original campaign design focused on a single school site, where two air quality sensors would be installed: one on the roadside side of a hedge and the other behind it. The aim was to assess the potential of vegetation as a natural barrier to particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) from traffic emissions. This concept aligned with growing interest in nature-based solutions and was intended to generate locally relevant data to inform urban greening strategies.

However, following internal discussions and technical review, it became clear that the data collected from this setup would likely be inconclusive. Variables such as wind direction, sensor sensitivity, and inconsistent distances from the road introduced too many confounding factors to draw meaningful conclusions. As a result, the project team made the decision to revise the campaign's focus.

Strategic Pivot and Revised Approach

In consultation with colleagues from Dundee City Council's Active Travel and Environmental Health teams, the campaign was reoriented toward addressing a more immediate and actionable issue: vehicle idling outside schools. This shift was driven by the need for data that could support behaviour change messaging and align with existing city priorities around sustainable travel and public health.

Two schools, Glebelands Primary and North East Campus, were identified as suitable pilot sites. Both are located near busy roads, have documented concerns around idling during drop-off and pick-up times, and expressed interest in participating. The revised approach focuses on installing one air quality sensor at each school to monitor pollution levels in real time, with the goal of using the data to support awareness campaigns and classroom learning.

2.3 Areas of Focus and Technologies Used

Geographic Focus

The Air Quality Monitoring Campaign is being piloted at two school sites (Figure 13 and Figure 14) where idling in front of school gates is a common issue. These locations were selected based on their proximity to busy roads and existing concerns around vehicle idling during school drop-off and pick-up times, potentially affecting pupils walking into school. Both schools expressed interest in participating and were identified in collaboration with Dundee City Council's Active Travel and Environmental Health teams.

Figure 13. Map of Glebelands Primary School showing close proximity to major road, Arbroath Road.

Figure 14. Location of Northeast Campus.

The original concept focused on a single school site, where sensors would be placed on either side of a roadside hedge to explore the potential of vegetation in reducing particulate matter. However, this approach was revised due to concerns about data reliability, influenced by environmental variables such as wind direction, sensor sensitivity, and inconsistent distances from the road. The pivot to a behaviour-focused model allowed for a more actionable and policy-aligned intervention.

Technologies Used

The campaign uses PurpleAir PA-II-SD sensors (Figure 15), which are low-cost, dual-laser particle counters designed to measure real-time concentrations of airborne particulate matter (PM1.0, PM2.5, and PM10). These sensors also record temperature, humidity, and pressure using a built-in BME280 sensor. Data is transmitted via Wi-Fi to the PurpleAir map, where it is publicly accessible and can be used for educational and advocacy purposes. [\[www2.purpleair.com\]](http://www2.purpleair.com)

Figure 15. PurpleAir Sensor.

To accommodate the lack of reliable power and Wi-Fi infrastructure at the selected school sites, the project team developed an off-grid setup consisting of:

- **Two rechargeable batteries** (Figure 16) per site with one battery powering the sensor, and the other powering the router.
- **One mobile Wi-Fi router** (Figure 17) enables real-time data transmission without relying on school networks.
- **One outdoor enclosure box** to protect the equipment from weather and tampering.

This modular setup ensures flexibility in sensor placement and allows the campaign to operate independently of school infrastructure. It also supports future replication in other locations with similar constraints.

Figure 16. 56800mAh Power Bank 30W.

Figure 17. TP-Link M7000 4G MiFi, Portable Travel Wi-Fi Device, 4g Router.

Citizen Science and Accessibility Considerations

While full implementation is still pending, the technologies selected are intended to support accessible citizen science. The PurpleAir platform provides open access to live and historical data, which can be used by pupils, teachers, and community members to explore environmental trends and support classroom learning by using real world data relevant to the pupils. Future adaptations may include simplified dashboards, printed data summaries, or guided activities to ensure usability across different age groups and digital access levels.

2.4 Citizen Engagement and Data Collection

Although the Air Quality Monitoring Campaign is still in its pre-implementation phase, citizen participation is a central component of its design. The campaign aims to introduce school pupils and their communities to environmental monitoring through accessible, real-time data collection and interpretation.

Types of Data and Collection Methods

The campaign will generate environmental data, specifically measurements of particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) using PurpleAir PA-II-SD sensors. These sensors collect data every two minutes and transmit it to an open-access platform, where it can be viewed live or downloaded for analysis. The data includes:

- PM_{1.0}, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ concentrations
- Temperature, humidity, and pressure readings

Tools and Platforms

The primary tools used in the campaign include:

- **PurpleAir PA-II-SD sensors:** Dual-laser particle counters with integrated environmental sensors.
- **PurpleAir online map:** A public platform for viewing live and historical air quality data.
- **Off-grid setup:** Each site includes two rechargeable batteries (one for the sensor, one for the router), a mobile Wi-Fi router, and a weatherproof outdoor enclosure. This configuration ensures flexibility and accessibility, especially in areas without reliable infrastructure.

Engagement Structure and Inclusion

Citizen engagement is structured around ongoing participation, with schools acting as long-term hosts of the sensors. Pupils will be encouraged to explore the data as part of science, geography, and maths lessons, and may lead their own investigations or awareness campaigns. Special efforts have been made to include schools in areas with known air quality concerns and limited access to environmental data. The selection of Glebelands Primary and Northeast Campus reflects a commitment to working with communities that may be disproportionately affected by traffic pollution. While no personal or demographic data will be collected through the sensor platform itself, future engagement activities may include optional surveys or feedback forms to help monitor inclusion and diversity in participation.

Use of Data by Stakeholders

The data collected through the campaign is intended to support:

- **Local government messaging:** Dundee City Council's Environmental Health and Active Travel teams can use the data to reinforce anti-idling campaigns and promote sustainable travel.
- **School-based learning:** Teachers can integrate the data into classroom activities, encouraging pupils to interpret trends and consider solutions.
- **Community awareness:** Parents and local residents can access the data to better understand pollution patterns and advocate for change.

Sharing Results and Adjustments

Results will be shared with participating schools through direct access to the PurpleAir platform, as well as through tailored summaries and visualisations where needed. These may include printed dashboards, simplified graphs, or classroom posters to support younger learners and families with limited digital access.

The campaign has already undergone significant adjustments, including:

- A pivot from vegetation impact monitoring to behaviour-focused school zone monitoring.
- A shift from mains-powered sensors to a fully off-grid setup to overcome infrastructure barriers.

These changes reflect a responsive and collaborative design process, ensuring that the campaign remains relevant, feasible, and impactful.

2.5 Findings and Reflections

At the time of reporting, no air quality data has yet been collected or analysed as part of the Air Quality Campaign, as the sensors have not yet been installed, and therefore no findings are currently evident. The campaign will collect continuous, hyper-local air quality data over time.

The monitoring approach has been informed by reported local concerns around vehicle idling, particularly during school pick-up and drop-off periods. It is anticipated that variations in air quality may be observed during these peak times compared to other periods of the day, providing an opportunity to better understand the relationship between traffic behaviour, school travel patterns and local environmental conditions. These anticipated comparisons will form a key focus of future analysis once sufficient data has been gathered.

All data generated through the PurpleAir network will be publicly accessible in real time via the PurpleAir website. This open-access model ensures transparency and enables participating schools, pupils, community groups and partners to view and engage with the data as it is collected. The availability of live data is intended to support environmental learning, encourage reflection on everyday behaviours such as idling, and provide an evidence base to inform future engagement activity, policy discussions and potential interventions once analysis is complete.

2.6 Recommendations and Future Steps

Next steps for the Air Quality Campaign include the installation of air quality sensors at the two participating school sites, followed by close working with teaching staff to support access to the PurpleAir data and ensure the monitoring process operates smoothly. Practical considerations, including the ongoing maintenance of the sensors such as regular battery replacement, will be addressed as part of this phase. Discussions are underway to determine the most appropriate approach to maintenance, including whether this will be managed by the Urban ReLeaf Officer or supported by the schools themselves, potentially creating opportunities for increased ownership and engagement.

The campaign timeline has been further delayed due to the recent change in the Dundee City Council Urban ReLeaf Officer role, and a new officer will need to be recruited and trained before the next phase can be fully implemented.

Appendices

Appendix A – Re-designed Paper Survey

About Urban ReLeaf

Urban ReLeaf is Dundee's biggest
Citizen Science Project!

We want to hear from you about the city's
greenspaces – what you love, what could be better,
and how they make you feel. Your feedback will help
shape greener, more enjoyable spaces for everyone.

Will you share your thoughts with us?

Tell us about you

Age: _____ Gender: _____ Postcode: _____

Education:

- Primary education Secondary education University education

Occupation or employment status:

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="radio"/> Working full-time | <input type="radio"/> Working part-time |
| <input type="radio"/> Temporarily away from work | <input type="radio"/> Unemployed |
| <input type="radio"/> On parental leave | <input type="radio"/> Any other kind of paid work |
| <input type="radio"/> Full-time student | <input type="radio"/> Full-time school pupil |
| <input type="radio"/> Long-term away from work | <input type="radio"/> Full-time carer |
| <input type="radio"/> Other: _____ | |

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| <input type="radio"/> On parental leave | <input type="radio"/> Any other kind of paid work |
| <input type="radio"/> Full-time student | <input type="radio"/> Full-time school pupil |
| <input type="radio"/> Long-term away from work | <input type="radio"/> Full-time carer |
| <input type="radio"/> Other: _____ | |

Tell us about the space you're in

Location: _____

Date: _____ **Time:** _____

How did you get here?

- Walked Cycled Car Bus
- Taxi Wheeled Other: _____

Was it easy to get here?

- ————— —————
- Not easy Very easy

Why was it easy or hard?

Why are you here today?

- Walking a dog Exercising Meeting friends Relaxing
- Going to work / shops Attending an event
- Other: _____

How often do you visit this space?

- A lot Sometimes Rarely First time

What do you like about this space?

- It's green
- Play
- Woodland
- Parking
- Trees
- Toilets
- Pond
- Water
- Has cool stuff
- Easy to get around
- Walking/running routes
- Other: _____

Finding your way around

—————

Super easy Really hard

What sounds do you hear?

- Traffic
- Wind
- Quiet
- Talking
- Kids playing
- Birds
- Other: _____

Wildlife sightings?

- Birds
- Deer
- Fox
- Squirrel
- Bats
- Bees
- Rabbits
- Insects
- Butterflies
- None
- Other: _____

How much litter is here?

—————

None A lot

Is everything kept clean and working well?

- Yes
- No

How safe do you feel here?

Why do you feel this way?

How windy is it?

What changes could we make to improve your experience of this park?

Sketch your current location:

How long do you plan to stay here today?

- Under 5 mins 5-10 mins 10 - 30 mins 30 mins - 1 hr
1-2 hrs Over 2 hrs I don't know

What would make you stay here longer?

What do you love about the space?

What do you dislike about the space?

Did you notice any flooding/standing water?

Tell us what you see:

Did you notice any dry areas e.g. brown grass or withering plants?

Tell us what you see:

Get involved

To stay updated on this project,
share your email.

Or email us at
urban.releaf@dundeecity.gov.uk

If you see something
broken or dangerous
please report to
[environment@
dundeecity.gov.uk](mailto:environment@dundeecity.gov.uk)

Scan to
find out more!

[https://bit.ly/
URDundee](https://bit.ly/URDundee)
[@releafcities](#)
[#releafcities](#)

What could we change to make it easier and safer to walk, wheel, cycle, scoot, skateboard or blade to this space?
Tell us:

If you see something broken or dangerous please report to environment@dundeecity.gov.uk

Play survey

Scan to find out more!

<https://bit.ly/URDundee>
#releafcities @releafcities

Location:

How safe and welcoming does this play space feel?

- Very welcoming
- Quite welcoming
- Quite unwelcoming
- Not welcoming

What do you like about this play space?

Is there anything you don't like about this play space?

What would make this play space better? Please tick all that apply:

- Equipment like slides, swings and roundabouts
- Adventurous equipment like zip wires and high ropes
- Opportunities for risky play, like building things with wood, hammers and nails
- Natural things, like trees, grass and plants
- Sports equipment like football pitches, tennis courts or basketball hoops
- Areas to hang out with small groups of friends
- Sheltered areas
- Access to Wifi
- Good quality, clean toilets
- Adults to help if needed
- Equipment for disabled children (mixed ability inclusive / accessible play equipment)
- Spaces to hang out without adults watching
- If it was cleaner
- Anything else?

Does this play space cater for different age groups? If so, which ones?

- 0-4
- 5-11
- 12-15
- 16-17

Appendix B – List of Dundee Parks and Greenspaces Surveyed

1. Parks

- Downfield Playing Fields
- Drumgeith Park
- Dudhope Park
- Eadies Park
- Fairmuir Park
- Finlathen Park
- Fintry Park
- Gillies Park
- Hilltown Park
- Kellyfield Park
- Lochee Park
- Magdalen Green
- Middleton Woods
- Mill O Mains Park
- Moneymusk Park
- Myrekirk Park
- Orchar Park
- Reres Hill
- Riverside Nature Park
- Slessor Gardens
- South Road Park
- St Leonards Park
- Victoria Park
- Western Cemetery

2. Cemeteries

- Balgay Cemetery
- Barnhill Cemetery
- Birkhill Cemetery
- Eastern Cemetery
- Greater Balgay
- The Howff
- The Law
- Western Cemetery

3. SUDS (Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems)

- Ardler East SUDS
- Ardler West SUDS
- Gillburn Road SUDS
- Mill O Mains SUDS
- Summerfield Avenue SUDS
- Waterfront SUDS

4. Notable Landmarks / Nature Reserves

- Broughty Ferry LNR
- Riverside Nature Park
- Templeton Woods
- Trottick Ponds
- Stobsmuir Ponds